

State of the art review and initial design of 6GSMART zero touch automation and service assurance mechanisms

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Acronyms

3GPP	3 rd Generation Partnership Project
5G	5 th Generation
5G-ACIA	5G Alliance for Connected Industries and Automation
5GC	5G Core
5GPPP	5G Infrastructure Public Private Partnership
6G	6 th Generation
AF	Application Function
AGV	Automated Guided Vehicle
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIOTI	Alliance for the Internet Of Things Innovation
AMF	Access and Mobility Management Function
AP	Access Point
API	Application Programming Interface
AR	Augmented Reality
AWS	Amazon Web Services
B5G	Beyond 5G
BGP	Border Gateway Protocol
CEI	Cloud-edge-IoT
CNI	Container Network Interface
CORC	Continuum ORChestrator
COTS	Commercial off-the-shelf
CPE	Customer Premise Equipment
CPPSoS	Cyber Physical Production Systems of Systems
CPS	Cyber Physical System
CPU	Central Processing Unit
CSC	Communication Service Customer
CSP	Communication Service Provider
CU-UP	Centralized Unit – User Plane
CUPS	Control User Plane Separation
CU	Centralised Unit
DL-AoD	Downlink Angle of departure
DL-TDOA	Downlink time difference of arrival
DNN	Data Network Name
DNS	Domain Name System
DPDK	Data Plane Development Kit
DU	Distributed Unit
E2E	End-to-End
E-CID	Enhanced cell ID

ECN	Edge Compute Network
ECOMP	Enhanced Control, Orchestration, Management and Policy
ECS	Amazon Elastic Container Service
EKS	Kubernetes Service
eMBB	Enhanced Mobile Broadband
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute
EUCEI	EU Cloud Edge IoT
FCAPS	Fault, Configuration, Accounting, Performance, and Security
FENS	Factory Edge Network Service
GCP	Google Cloud Platform
GDC	Google Distributed Cloud
GNSS	Global Navigation Satellite Systems
GPS	Global Positioning System
GPU	Graphics Processing Unit
GTP	GPRS Tunnelling Protocol (GTP)
GSMA	GSM (Groupe Spéciale Mobile) Association
GW	Gateway
I4.0	Industry 4.0
ICC	Industrial Cloud Continuum
ICT	Information and Communication Technologies
IoT	Internet of Things
IIoT	Industrial Internet of Things
IT	Information Technology
K8s	Kubernetes
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
LKC	Linux Kernel Containers
LoS	Line Of Sight
LST&P	Large Scale Trials and Pilots
MANO	Management and Orchestration
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
MIMO	Multiple Input Multiple Output
ML	Machine Learning
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations
mMTC	Massive Machine Type Communication
MNO	Mobile Network Operator
MOCN	Multi Operator Core Network
MPTCP	Multi-path TCP
NEF	Network Exposure Function
NF	Network Functions
NFV	Network Function Virtualisation
NG-RAN	New Generation Radio Access Network
NOP	Network OPERator

NPN	Non-Public Networks
NR	New Radio
NSA	Non-standalone
NSaaS	Network Slicing as a Service
NSSF	Network Slice Selection Function
NWDAF	Network Data Analytics Function
OAI	Open Air Interface
OCM	Open Cloud Mesh
OGC	Ori Global Cloud
ONAP	Open Network Automation Platform
OP	Operator Platform
OPC-UA	Open Platform Communications Unified Architecture
OPEX	Operational Expenditure
OS	Operating System
OSG	Open-Source Group
OSM	Open-Source MANO
OT	Operational Technology
PLC	Programmable Logic Controller
QCI	QoS Class Identifier
QoS	Quality of Service
RAN	Radio Access Network
RAT	Radio Access Technology
RIC	RAN Intelligent Controller
RRF	Recovery and Resilience Facility
RT	Real-Time
SA	Standalone
SBA	Service Based Architecture
SCS	Sub Carrier Spacing
SDG	Sustainable Development Goals
SDK	Software Development Kit
SDN	Software-Defined Networking
SDO	Standards Developing Organisations
SEP	Service Enablement Platform
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SMF	Session Management Function
S-NSSAI	Single – Network Slice Selection Assistance Information
SNS JU	Software Networks & Services Joint Undertaking
SSID	Service Set Identifier
TAC	Tracking Area Code
THz	TeraHertz
TSCTSF	Time Sensitive communication Time Synchronization Function
TSN	Time Sensitive Networking

UE	User Equipment
UL-AoA	Uplink Angle of arrival
UL-TDOA	Uplink time difference of arrival
UN	United Nations
UNICO	Univerzalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
UPF	User Plane Function
URLLC	Ultra-Reliable and Low-Latency Communication
US	United States
UWB	Ultra Wide Band
VAN	Virtual Application Network
VIM	Virtual Infrastructure Manager
VM	Virtual Machine
VNS	Virtual Network Services
VPC	Virtual Private Cloud
VPP	Vector Packet Processing
VPN	Virtual Private Network
WAT	Wireless Access Technology
WG	Working Group
XR	Extended Reality

Executive Summary

This document corresponds to deliverable “D2.1.1 - State of the art review and initial design of 6GSMART zero touch automation and service assurance mechanisms” of the subproject 6GSMART-EZ, “6G for Smart Cyber Physical Production Systems of Systems – extreme KPIs and Zero Touch Automation“, which is devoted to the research on Extreme KPIs and Zero Touch Automation. Particularly, this document presents the contributions from i2CAT to the task devoted to the study and design of solutions aiming at enhancing zero-touch automation of 5G networks in Industry 5.0.

The deliverable introduces three main contributions related to zero-touch RAN automation: (i) RAN service provisioning, (ii) RAN configuration and (iii) RAN diagnostics. For each solution, relevant state of the art and initial design is provided, describing the main envisioned steps towards its implementation and evaluation. All three solutions follow a practical approach, targeting easy integration with non-public networks in industrial environments.

1. Introduction

6GSMART is an R&D project under the Spanish UNICO framework that investigates how 5G technology needs to evolve to address the unique needs of presented by Operational Technologies (OT). This deliverable presents the initial work developed within the scope of 6GSMARTEZ subproject, which is devoted to the research on Extreme KPIs and Zero Touch Automation. The goal of this subproject is to develop networking enablers that push forward 5G KPIs in terms of throughput, latency and localization, as well as management enablers that simplify the operations of 5G/6G networks in manufacturing environments.

Providing zero-touch network automation is a key challenge in 5G and B5G in order to cope with the growing complexity of the networks. 5G native features such as virtualization, softwarisation, programmability, cloud-nativeness, end-to-end slicing, RAN disaggregation or edge computing, among others, lead to complex systems hard to operate, manage and evolve by mobile operators [1]. This becomes more problematic in the case of non-public networks (NPN) due to the lack of human experts in industrial environments. Therefore, minimizing dependence on humans to operate, optimise and maintain the network is crucial to foster the adoption of NPNs in Industry 5.0.

Several standardization bodies such as ETSI¹, 3GPP² or O-RAN³ are considering zero-touch automation as a key topic, working on the standardization of interfaces, functions and components that can enable it in multi-vendor and multi-domain environments. This is accomplished by providing mechanisms which allow implementing and exposing monitoring, analytics and control features, which can be then exploited by control-loop automations. The incorporation of AI/ML will further empower these automations, allowing to perform proactive operations based on predictions.

In addition to automations, in industrial environments it is also highly relevant to facilitate the interaction with network systems. This can be accomplished by intent-based approaches, which capture the high-level objectives of users and conveying them to actions or configurations. Additionally, the seamless integration of 5G NPNs and the networks already present in the industrial environments is a key requirement to avoid disrupting the operation of vertical services.

In this context, in this task of 6GSMART we will focus on zero-touch automations targeting the RAN domain. Following a practical approach, we have selected solutions which can be easily adopted by industry verticals and integrated by NPN providers. In particular, we consider the following topics related to zero-touch RAN automation:

- Zero-touch RAN service provisioning: Relates to the provisioning of network services over a RAN infrastructure, while minimizing the required manual interventions and configurations.
- Zero-touch RAN configuration: Relates to the configuration of the network infrastructure, which should use a declarative approach, whereby the network

¹ <https://www.etsi.org/technologies/zero-touch-network-service-management>

² <https://www.3gpp.org/technologies/mda-sa5>

³ <https://orandownloadsweb.azurewebsites.net/specifications>

operator defines the desired state, and the management system should proactively check the current configuration and adjust it to the desired state if needed.

- Zero-touch RAN diagnostics: Relates to the automated analysis of network faults, whereby the diagnostics systems can pin-point situations where the RAN does not perform as expected and assist the network operator in debugging the current problem.

In this deliverable, which is structured as follows, we introduce relevant state of the art and the initial design for a proposed solution in each of these domains.

- Section 2 reports relevant state of the art and the initial design of the solution dealing with RAN service provisioning.
- Section 3 reports relevant state of the art and the initial design of the solution dealing with RAN configuration.
- Section 4 reports relevant state of the art and the initial design of the solution dealing with RAN diagnostics.
- Section 5 concludes the deliverable by summarizing its main topics and expounding future work in the related tasks.

2. 6GSMART approach to zero-touch RAN service provisioning

A primary aspect of 5G networks is their ability to provide tailored radio access, core, and transport networks that are adjusted to meet the specific needs of various industries, known as vertical services. These services necessitate a network architecture that is both flexible and built on cloud-native principles. Functionalities already provided by 4G, such as Multi-Operator Core Networks (MOCN) or Control User Plane Separation (CUPS), have been further extended with 5G network slicing, allowing the creation of logical networks adapted to the use case needs which may share a common physical infrastructure. This high flexibility also entails a high complexity to ensure a correct and efficient zero-touch RAN service provisioning, requiring of an orchestration framework capable of dealing with the configuration all the domains.

In addition to provisioning a service-tailored RAN, one fundamental aspect in Industry 5.0 is to provide a seamless integration of the new NPN network and the network architecture already present. This is needed to avoid impacting services, which, for instance, need to be connected to a specific L2 or L3 network. To this end, this section presents the state of the art and the initial design related to the 6GSMART solution.

2.1 State of the art

Related to zero-touch RAN service provisioning, the 5G-CLARITY project developed a RAN controller [2] able to configure Mobile Network Operator (MNO) services over a shared infrastructure by leveraging the Multi-Operator Core Network (MOCN) feature and configuring the advertised PLMNID/S-NSSAI values in the cells of a gNB, as well as the transport VLAN used to communicate with a given core network. The proposed platform also considered instantiating multiple core networks at the edge, but did not support distributed UPFs, which resulted in excessive use of compute resources at the edge. Another relevant work is [3], where the authors define an intent-driven architecture that allows an operator to provision services using natural language, such as “*I want to provision a network slice*”. A drawback of their approach is that the proposed architecture cannot be easily generalized beyond the three use cases presented in the paper.

In [4] we presented i2Slicer, a flexible solution to orchestrate the deployment of 5G standalone end-to-end network slices with multi-tenancy and multi-service capabilities. This solution is based on two frameworks developed and demonstrated by i2CAT within the scope of different H2020 projects: the Slice Manager and the RAN Controller. On the one hand, the Slice Manager is responsible for orchestrating the overall lifecycle of E2E network slices, coordinating the deployment and configuration of Core, RAN and transport domains. On the other hand, the RAN Controller interacts with the RAN nodes to allow dynamic and remote configuration of RAN services. In [4] we described the

integration of the i2Slicer with Open5Gs⁴ open source 5G Core and with Amarisoft RAN⁵ solutions. Similarly, in [5] the i2Slicer solution was integrated with a different RAN solution, based on disaggregated Open RAN and aligned with the O-RAN Alliance⁶.

The seamless integration of different network segments into a common network is a key aspect for successfully deploying NPN in Industry 5.0 scenario [6]. First, in scenarios such as factories, the deployment of the new 5G network should not disrupt the activity of the up & running network, also minimizing the impact on IT operations such as configuring routers or firewalls. Second, nodes connected to the 5G NPN network, such as sensors or cameras, should have the same type of connectivity than nodes connected to other networks.

Figure 2-1: Integration of 5G Networks on L3 and L2 [6]

Usually, 5G networks apply Network Address Translation (NAT) at the UPF to connect the 5G private IP subnet (between UEs and UPF) to the network behind the UPF. This adds complexity in cases when external applications require to open a connect to the 5G UEs. 5G supports Framed Routing [7], which allows to declare subnets being routed by a specific UE, configuring the UPF to appropriately route the packets. However, this solution is meant for cases where 5G UEs are managing different IP subnets, while in industrial scenarios the key point is usually to integrate them in a common IP network.

Indeed, due to the prevalence of Ethernet technologies in industrial environments [6], usually Layer-2 (L2) connectivity is needed. For instance, this is one of the main requirements reported for one of the 6GSMART use cases [8]. Also, the integration of 5G with Time Sensitive Networking (TSN) requires of L2 connectivity [9]. To this end, in the next section we present the 6GSMART approach to provide L2 seamless integration of 5G NPN networks during service provisioning.

2.2 Initial design

Figure 2-2 shows the multi-service and multi-tenant architecture that can be accomplished by using i2Slicer on top of Open5Gs 5G Core and Amarisoft 5G RAN

⁴ <https://open5gs.org/>

⁵ <https://www.amarisoft.com/test-and-measurement/device-testing/device-products>

⁶ <https://www.o-ran.org/>

solutions. This is the baseline architecture being considered in 6GSMART, although in industrial environments MOCN functionalities will not be required. Note that each different colour in the RAN interfaces (N2, N3, N4 and N6) denote a different VLAN; i.e., we are able to automate the configuration of VLANs to isolate the common control plane and the different user and data planes of the different slices. Also, data plane VLAN also includes Wi-Fi UEs belonging to the same slice. This approach could be adequate for scenarios where the 5G NPN is isolated from the rest of the local network (i.e., independent service). However, in integrated scenarios, it requires a strict planification of the IP connectivity at the 5G Core and the data network to avoid conflicts with IP assignment and routing (e.g., by applying subnetting).

Figure 2-2: i2Slicer network slicing architecture [4].

However, the industrial use cases being considered in 6GSMART consider additional requirements which require of modifications or enhancements on this baseline architecture. First, NPN UEs are industrial Customer Provided Equipment (CPEs) capable of aggregating 5G and Wi-Fi by using solutions such as MultiPath TCP (MPTCP) or Multi-link VPN (MLVPN). This approach also needs the deployment of an element after the UPF terminating the MPTCP or MLVPN connection. Secondly, the CPE will act as a network element, providing access to the 5G NPN to the nodes involved in the service, such as cameras. Figure 2-3 illustrates this architecture, where the Firewall is an element already present in the network which only allows connections from specific VLANs and connects to the applications servers.

Figure 2-3: High-level architecture of the targeted use case [8]

To implement this approach, in 6GSMART we will study the utilisation of Virtual Extensible LANs (VxLAN) technologies to provide seamless E2E connectivity between the application servers and the nodes through the 5G NPN network. VxLAN is a network virtualization technology used to extend Layer 2 networks over Layer 3 networks. It encapsulates Ethernet frames within IP packets, offering a more scalable and flexible approach than VLANs, which are restricted to Layer 2 domains.

Figure 2-4 depicts the envisioned architecture when using Multi-RAT CPEs and L2 Multipath Termination Proxy based on VxLAN. Using VxLAN offers 3 main advantages. First, in the 5G network, it permits to create VLANs on top of the point-to-point tunnels between UEs and the UPFs. Secondly, it uses periodic keepalive messages to maintain connectivity, what avoids UEs going to idle mode; this is interesting in industrial environments to achieve URLLC performance. Finally, as show in Figure 2-4, it permits to reuse VxLANs terminations in the Proxy for all CPEs, thus avoiding scalability issues.

Figure 2-4: L2 architecture including CPE and L2 Multipath Termination Proxy (VxLAN)

While the performance of Wi-Fi and 5G aggregation using MPTCP will be studied in detail within other 6GSMART-EX tasks [9], in this task we will focus on:

- Requirements and configurations to provide seamless connectivity: Deals with the definition of required components, IP connectivity, VXLAN and VLANs, aggregation solutions, etc.
- Performance evaluation of the solution: Deals with the evaluation of the E2E solution and of different alternatives (if any) in terms of performance (e.g., throughput, latency, etc.).

3. 6GSMART approach to zero-touch RAN configuration

Closed loops are key enablers for automation, enabling zero-touch management of RAN components to minimize human intervention [10]. Operations such as self-monitor, self-evaluate and self-heal are mandatory to simplify the operation of complex systems such as the 5G networks, including the support of features such as network slicing, virtualization, cloud-native operation, etc. Additionally, the integration with intent-based networking approaches, which are based on abstracted high-level requirements to define objectives, can facilitate the operation of closed-loops and the interactions among them.

In industrial environments, once the network has been deployed, minimizing the impact of day-2 operations (e.g., maintaining, monitoring, and optimizing) is key to assure service availability and reduce operational costs. To this end, this section presents the state of the art and the initial design of the 6GSMART-EZ solution aiming at automating RAN reconfigurations.

3.1 State of the art

Related to zero-touch RAN network configuration, several RAN management platforms have recently appeared that enable a simplified and API-driven configuration of RAN infrastructure. For example, FlexRAN [11] was a configuration agent for OAI-based gNBs that later evolved into FlexRIC [12] with the ability to embed xApps. A drawback of these RAN configuration platforms is that only support OAI-based gNBs, and cannot detect local changes in the RAN configuration, which may result in drifts between the desired configuration state and the actual configuration in the RAN devices. Lack of automated configuration drift detection is a big problem for example when managing many private networks remotely.

Zero-touch configuration requires a mechanism for active reconciliation, whereby drifts from the intended configuration state can be detected and proactively solved. The state of the art in active reconciliation is the operator framework defined by Kubernetes (K8s) for cloud-native applications [13]. The operator framework is based on using Custom Resource Definitions (CRDs) in K8s to specify the desired state of an infrastructure resource, e.g. number of pods for a given service. Thus, K8s implements a series of controllers that check the definitions in the CRD against the actual state of the infrastructure, and proactively resolve any conflict, e.g. instantiating a new pod if needed.

In [14] authors present Kube5G, a cloud-native 5G Service platform which uses Kubernetes Operators to automate the application lifecycle management in runtime. This framework, available through the Mosaic 5G community⁷, implements the following functionalities: (i) deployment and release, (ii) configuration and reconfiguration, (iii) network update, upgrade, and downgrade, (iv) network re-aggregation, disaggregation, and (v) CNF monitoring (health and metrics). The work in [15] deals with the utilization of Kubernetes Operators to dynamically adapt the configuration of the UPF according to

⁷ <https://mosaic5g.io/kube5g/#software>

intents coming from applications at the Edge. In particular, the application can request local-breakout as a service without the need of understanding the networking in that particular site.

3.2 Initial design

In 6GSMART we will study how to extend the K8s operator framework to manage desired configuration of RAN infrastructure. We envision a configuration system such as the one depicted in Figure 3-1, where the operator defines the desired configuration state, which is then used as ground truth for the system. Upon reboots, unintended manual configurations, or power outages, the 6GSMART configuration system will make sure that the RAN resource is reverted to the intended configuration, without requiring any manual intervention from the network operator.

Figure 3-1: 6GSMART zero-touch RAN configuration system

The proposed methodology to carry out this work will be using a laboratory testbed based on an Amarisoft RAN. The Amarisoft configuration system is based on a set of configuration files that are manually edited. As introduced in previous Chapter, in previous projects i2CAT already developed RAN Controller that allows to remotely control Amarisoft configuration files through a NETCONF interface. The goal in 6GSMART will be to develop a K8s operator that is able to control RAN configuration in the Amarisoft boxes making use of the Netconf interface. Figure 3-2 illustrates the envisioned integration of K8S operators and the RAN Controller, where the Amarisoft Operator is now in charge of configuring, monitoring and reconfiguring the Amarisoft boxes according to the service definition stored in the Custom Resource Definitions (CRDs).

Figure 3-2: Integration of the RAN Controller and Kubernetes Operators to manage Amarisoft RAN.

A lab-based demonstration will be performed, showcasing how the 6GSMART configuration system reverts any intended misconfiguration in the Amarisoft box to the desired state. To evaluate it, we will create a set of tests and verify its successfully operation. Additionally, we will analyse performance KPIs such as the reconfiguration latency.

4. 6GSMART approach to zero-touch RAN diagnostics

The application of AI/ML methods to the management of cellular networks is key to support the increase of network flexibility and complexity of 5G and B5G, while ensuring security, reliability and allocation of the necessary resources to their customers in a dynamic robust and trustworthy way [16]. Particularly, its application to network planning, network diagnostic and network optimisation can bring substantial benefits and will be key to enable zero-touch automation. Regarding network diagnostic, historically operators have depended on expertise to pinpoint issues within an operational mobile network [16]. However, autonomous zero-touch diagnostic tools are needed, especially in NPN scenarios where human expert diagnosis is not feasible and will impact maintenance cost, thus limiting NPN adoption.

In this Section we analyse the state of the art related to AI/ML-driven RAN diagnostics, presenting the initial design of the 6GSMART contribution towards this research topic.

4.1 State of the art

In [16] authors analyse solutions proposed by H2020 projects related to AI/ML-driven network diagnostics, considering the following categories: (i) Forecasting network characteristics and events, (ii) estimating user location, and (iii) forecasting security incidents. Regarding the first category, which is the most relevant to our work, forecasting strategies can help to identify network aspects impacting KPIs related to Quality of Service (QoS), Quality of Experience (QoE) or Service Level Agreements, enabling the introduction of monitoring, detection, and resolution solutions. Also, it can help to identify and predict complex events to avoid undesired situations and optimise networks to prevent them.

Authors propose in [17] a zero-touch system to detect cells that are not performing well in a mobile network. The proposed system uses Call Data Records to feed an AI-pipeline composed of K-means and Support Vector Machines (SVMs) that can identify underperforming cells. Subsequently, and aided with network topology information, the proposed scheme can pin-point the root cause for the observed performance problems. A drawback of this paper is that it only addresses voice related traffic.

In [18] uses time series forecasting to predict threats which can lead to system failure in the 5G Core. The prediction algorithm considers as input actual and predicted traffic to forecast the CPU and memory usage of core network functions, the average operation duration for different procedures in the 5G Core, and the rate of operation failures. The predictions of these parameters are used as input to decide if a system failure will occur.

The advent of AI and its massive application to prediction and control operations has raised the need to understand the decisions made by AI models. To this end, Explainable AI (XAI) methods can be used. Authors in [19] apply explainability methods to identify features contributing to the prediction of SLA violations, aiming at detecting the root causes. In [20], XAI methods are used to explain predictions related to QoE, leveraging a dataset conceived for the estimation of the user-perceived video quality.

4.2 Initial design

The design of the 6GSMART solution for zero-touch RAN diagnostics will be based on two main subsystems. Figure 4-1 depicts the functional architecture of these two subsystems, together with some envisioned workflows, which are described as follows:

Figure 4-1: Functional architecture of the 6GSMART RAN diagnostics solution.

- RAN observability:** This subsystem enables the monitoring in non-real-time (period equal or higher to 1s) of the RAN, including the gNBs and the UEs (1). Telemetry from other domains such as the 5G Core, the application or computing domain, could be also integrated if needed. Data is stored in a Time-series database (TSDB), which can be exposed through an API to internal or external visualization frameworks, and to the AI-driven RAN diagnostic for dataset generation (2) and inference (4). We will use Prometheus⁸ and Grafana⁹ to implement the RAN observability subsystem, being aligned with the partner from 6GSMART-EZ providing the NPN solution.
- AI-driven RAN Diagnosis:** This subsystem will use the RAN data to provide RAN diagnostic outputs based on ML models doing predictions and anomaly detections. Models will be trained according to the obtained RAN data (3), processed and stored in a dataset (2). Once trained, the models will be served, and their outputs used to provide RAN diagnostics (5). These diagnostics will be

⁸ <https://prometheus.io/>

⁹ <https://grafana.com/>

exposed in the RAN Observability, to facilitate its visualization by the tenants. Additionally, alarms could be created according to diagnosed performance or anomalies. MLOps Frameworks such as MLRun¹⁰ or MLFlow¹¹ will be considered to implement this subsystem.

Regarding the ML models, they will be based on time series since we can assume that the utilization of NPNs in industrial environments will follow a predictable pattern dependent on the day of the week and time. On the one hand, traffic related to industrial applications is usually not dependent on user behaviour, being more predictable during working hours and days. On the other hand, UE mobility is usually restricted to the same paths, specifically in the case of autonomous UEs. This opens the door to the application of time series predictors and anomaly detectors, which can be applied to aggregated KPIs (i.e., per network, per area, per cell) or to individual UEs. In particular, we are considering the following KPIs, which are usually available in NPNs:

- Per cell KPIs: Cell load (e.g., % of cell utilisation), average throughput per UE, average channel quality indicator (CQI) per UE, average number of UEs, number of handovers, packet error rates...
- Per UE KPIs: Throughput, signal indicators (e.g., RSSI, RSRP), modulation and coding scheme (MCS), CQI...

Forecasting can be used to predict future values of time series, what can then be applied to detect anomalies. For instance, if the actual value of the cell load is far from the predicted value (i.e., according to a threshold), it can be a sign of an anomaly in the network. Combining it with other predictions, such as the number of UEs, the throughput or the CQ, the RAN diagnostics system could derive automatically the issue (e.g., higher number of UEs than expected). Among the algorithms being used for forecasting, we are considering Prophet [21] and XGBoost [22].

- The Prophet ML algorithm is a forecasting model developed by Facebook that is specifically designed for time series analysis, enabling users to predict future trends and patterns with high accuracy and flexibility. It also allows to incorporate information about holidays and events to improve the accuracy of the predictions. However, it is a univariate time series model, using the trend of individual variables.
- XGBoost is a scalable and efficient implementation of gradient boosting, known for its speed and performance in supervised learning tasks such as regression and classification. It builds a series of decision trees sequentially, where each subsequent tree corrects the errors of the previous ones, ultimately creating a strong ensemble model. It supports multivariate forecasting.

In addition to forecasting, we will consider algorithms more oriented to time series anomaly detection. Specially, algorithms based on unsupervised learning are interesting since they do not require to label anomaly data points. For instance, methods based on

¹⁰ <https://www.mlrun.org/>

¹¹ <https://mlflow.org/>

trees [23], clustering [24] or Deep Learning [25] are of interest and could be applied to this solution.

Once predictions and/or anomalies are determined, they will be used to diagnose the status and performance of the RAN. For instance, they might be combined to compute a RAN score value, helping tenants to easily determine if the network is performing well or not without needing to understand the different and numerous RAN metrics. Then, in case there is a performance degradation, anomaly detectors could pinpoint the root cause.

5. Conclusions

The efficient management of 5G and B5G networks require of specialized personnel, which is not usually available in the case of industry verticals. Therefore, the adoption of zero-touch automation approaches is key to fostering the integration of NPNs and local networks in Industry 5.0. Standardization efforts are dealing with the definition of interfaces, components, and functions capable of exposing monitoring, analytics and control operations, what will enable the implementation of intelligent control-loops.

In this deliverable, we have introduced three different solutions to facilitate the deployment of 5G RAN networks in the industry, focused on three different topics: RAN service deployment, RAN configuration and RAN diagnostics. For each of the proposed solutions, which follow a practical approach to facilitate its integration with NPNs, we have presented relevant state of the art and an initial design. Next deliverable will present the evaluation of these solutions, while integration within demonstrators will be reported in 6GSMART-EXP subproject.

6. References

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